

EFFECT OF THE CRYSTALLINITY ON THE BARRIER PROPERTIES OF PLA BASED NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Nanocomposites with cellulose nanofibers and/or commercially available nanoclay (Cloisite™ 30B) were prepared and evaluated for use in food packaging. Cellulose nanofibers were extracted from sisal fibers using an optimized three-step chemical protocol. In sequence, the steps were strong alkali treatment, a bleaching process, and finally an acetylation step. Nanocomposite films were prepared by solvent casting using an optimized method for each nanofiller or nanofiller combination. The combination of nanocellulose and nanoclay within a PLA matrix decreased dramatically the oxygen barrier properties (the PLA/CNF/C30B 1% 1% showed a 63% of decrease on the oxygen transmission rate (OTR) and the PLA/CNF/C30B 5% 5% showed a 88%), water barrier properties (the PLA/CNF/C30B 1% 1% showed a 57% of decrease on the water vapour barrier properties WVTR and the PLA/CNF/C30B 5% 5% a 75%), enhanced the thermomechanical properties and crystallization kinetic (the addition of 1% CNF and 1% of C30B reduced the half crystallization time of the PLA from 25 to 5 minutes) without a significant reduction on transparency. It was found that the addition of nanofillers to the matrix was leading to reduced water diffusion than the neat PLA but the nanocomposites with CNF showed also slightly higher water absorption than neat PLA and PLA/C30B. Moreover it was also found that bigger spherulite size leads to a higher decrease on diffusivity but also to slight increase in water sorption, the smaller spherulite size was leading to a reduction in both parameters. Finally the fully crystallized PLA/C30B/CNF 1% 1% nanocomposite showed a 45% of decrease on WVTR if compared with fully crystallized PLA meaning that the presence of both nanofillers even at low load can enhance the barrier properties of PLA.

1 INTRODUCTION

The use of petrochemical products for packaging applications represents a serious global issue, on one hand the use of non-renewable resources could lead to a lack of raw material and in the other hand the disposal of non-biodegradable resources. In order to solve the problem, in recent years, especially in the food packaging industry, a huge effort has been made in order to develop biobased and biodegradable materials in order to substitute the materials that are being used currently (i.e. PE and PET) for this purpose. For that reason, the use of biobased and biodegradable polymers such as PLA is generally finding an increasing number of applications. But the PLA still has inferior material performance compared to the classical polymers it is advocated to substitute. In particular, processing and mechanical properties of PLA such as e.g. brittleness, poor thermomechanical properties, slow crystallization, and medium barrier properties have been some of the major obstacles in expanding the application area of PLA (Madhavan Nampoothiri, Nair, & John, 2010).

During recent years several different strategies have been adopted in order to improve the properties of PLA. Among all of them, the use of nanofillers as cellulose nanofibers (CNF) or cellulose nanocrystals (CNW), has received the attention of numerous researchers not only for its biodegradability, bio-based origin and availability but also since it has great properties such as a specific young modulus, 3.4 times the one of the iron, (Eichhorn & Dufresne, 2010) which makes it a promising nanofiller for PLA. The addition of nanocellulose to PLA has several advantages such as a reinforcing effect of the CNF on PLA (Eichhorn & Dufresne, 2010), (Siqueira, Bras, & Dufresne, 2009), (Kowalczyk, Piorkowska, Kulpinski, & Pracella, 2011), (Fortunati, Peltzer, & Armentano, 2012), and a nucleating agent behaviour, thus enhancing crystallization kinetics (Kose & Kondo, 2013) of PLA. Finally, as long as the size of CNF is below the visible wavelength of the visible light if the CNF is properly dispersed in the matrix the transparency of the films should not be affected. Finally there are some studies on the use of nanocellulose to enhance the barrier properties of PLA but with a wide range of results. In the case of the oxygen barrier properties, to the knowledge of the authors, the best result is a decrease of 90% in the oxygen permeability achieved using 1% of CNW and PLA in dichloromethane by a freeze drying technique (Sanchez-Garcia, Lopez-Rubio, & Lagaron, 2010). There are also reports of moderate improvements on barrier properties of PLA films (9%-43%) (Fortunati et al., 2012) and finally there are reports of PLA nanocomposites reinforced with CNW showing reduced barrier properties than the neat PLA (Espino-Pérez et al., 2013).

Moreover, for the specific case of PLA the role of crystallinity of the water sorption is not clear and very different results can be observed at the literature, starting from a different behaviour on water sorption and diffusion depending on the test conditions (Siparsky, Voorhees, Dorgan, & Schilling, 1997), a water sorption decrease with increasing crystallinity (Cairncross, Becker, Ramaswamy, & O'Connor, 2006) and a water sorption increase with increased crystallization temperature or crystallinity (Koo, Du, Palmese, & Cairncross, 2012). This means that the study of barrier properties of PLA based nanocomposites is very challenging.

In previous works, a procedure to produce well dispersed nanocomposites with CNF and/or C30B was elaborated. Well dispersed neat PLA, PLA/C30B 1%, PLA/CNF 1% and PLA/CNF/C30B 1% 1% nanocomposites were submitted to a deeper study on the water vapour transmission rate by means of a QSM (Quartz Spring Microbalance). The samples were tested after solvent casting, after annealing (almost amorphous state) and after full isothermal crystallization at 120 °C for 120 min (in order to simulate the crystallinity that can be expected for commercially available polymers) and the water diffusion and water absorption was calculated.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 MATERIAL AND METHODS

The polylactic acid (Ingeo 2003D) was kindly supplied by Natureworks (Minnesota, MN, USA). The cellulose nanoreinforcements were extracted from sisal which was kindly supplied by Expor Sisal S.L. The nanoclays were the commercially available Cloisite 30B which is reported to have a cationic exchange capacity (CEC) of 90 and tetra alkyl ammonium salt as surfactant. Cloisite C30B is a commercially available nanoclay well described in the literature (Mohapatra, Mohanty, & Nayak, 2012), (Katiyar et al., 2010), (Rhim, Hong, & Ha, 2009). NaOH, sulphuric acid (95%-97%), nitric acid (ACS reagent, 70%), acetic acid (99%-100%), N, N – dimethyl formamide (98%, ACS reagent) and the dichloromethane (99, 8% chromasolv) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich and the sodium chlorite (25% w/w on water) from Merck. All of the reagents were used as received.

The dimension of the films (12 x 12 cm) were characterized by a digital micrometre with a tolerance of +/- 1% in 9 points (8 point in the side and 1 in the middle), before an examination with magnifying glasses to check for bubbles and other kind of contamination.

Thermal properties such as glass transition (T_g), melting (T_m) temperatures and degree of crystallinity (X_c) of PLA and the nanocomposites were determined by DSC (TA DSC Q1000) with a heating rate of 10 C/min in a range of 0 – 200 °C at 10 C/min in a heating/cooling/heating cycle. A melting enthalpy of 93 J g⁻¹ for 100% crystalline poly (L-lactide) was considered as reported (Ray & Okamoto, 2003). To determine X_c Eq 1 was used. The X_c was calculated both for the 1st heating cycle and second heating cycle.

$$X_c = \frac{1}{1-X_n} \frac{\Delta H_m - \Delta H_c}{\Delta H_0} \quad (1)$$

Where X_c is the degree of crystallinity of the composite, X_n the content of nanofiller, ΔH_m is the melting enthalpy (the area of the peak which minimum is at T_m) and ΔH_c is the crystallization enthalpy.

The oxygen transmission rate (OTR) was measured by triplicate using a Lyssy OPT-5000 Oxygen permeability tester, and was performed at 23 °C at 0% and 50% of RH. The results were expressed in (mL $\mu\text{m}^{-2} \text{day}^{-1}$).

The water vapour transmission rate (WVTR) of the films was measured by triplicate according to the norm NF H 00-030 at 23 °C and 50% RH using silica gel as desiccating agent with a specific exchange surface (S) 28.27 cm². The mass increase of the cups, due to the water absorption of silica gel was plotted against the time and the WVTR was calculated with Eq 2 where l is the thickness of the film.

$$WVTR = \frac{\text{Slope} * l}{S} \quad (2)$$

2.2 QUARTZ SPRING MICROBALANCE

The quartz spring, model 4501.6M from Ruska Instruments (Houston, TX), is non-rotating with a sensitivity of 1 mm/mg and can hold a maximum load of 50 mg. It is mounted inside a glass column with controlled temperature by a water jacket to within ± 0.5 °C through the experiment, 23 °C in this case. Stainless steel tubes and valves allow connections between the different parts of the apparatus and to the vacuum system; the latter contains vacuum pump with a liquid nitrogen trap used for the degassing and evacuation of the test vapour. The sample is observed through a CCD Camera (Series 600 Smartimage sensors) manufactured by The DVT Corporation (Norcross, GA) equipped with additional lenses (25 or 35 mm) and some extenders to optimize magnification and focal distance during different experiments and a strobe led array illuminator, model IDRA-6, is placed behind the glass column to achieve the optimal illumination and the maximum image contrast. By the use of a special algorithm, the light intensity existing in two adjacent pixels is recorded, processed and interpolated so that the original image (640 × 480 pixels) is reconstructed on a wider scale and the position of the edges is defined more precisely. The increment in sensitivity thus reached is ten times the sensitivity of the CCD camera alone.

The sample is linked to the hook through a copper wire with one piece of aluminium foil of well-known size and is used as a reference to convert distances from pixels units into length units. In the first step the balance and the feeding reservoir are under vacuum until the sample got dried (starting point). In the second step the testing liquid (in this case water) is stored in a bottle and vaporized into a 4 l reservoir. Once arrived to the desired pressure within the reservoir the valve which connects the balance and the reservoir is open and the penetrating liquid goes in vapour form to the balance. In this moment, the starting point of the experiment, the penetrating vapour starts being absorbed into the sample and the mass increase elongates the spring. Once the sample has arrived to the equilibrium at the working water activity the total amount of water absorbed can be easily calculated from the elongation and the diffusivity can be obtained from the plot of mass increase versus time through the use of models. After that the feeding reservoir can be filled again with more vapour and the

experiment can be repeated at higher water activity. As long as the water sorption of PLA use to show a linear behaviour below ~ 70% RH with 3 points a sorption isotherm can be obtained.

3 RESULTS

In previous works films of Neat PLA, PLA/CNF 1% (PLA + cellulose nanofibers), PLA/C30B 1% (PLA + nanoclay), and PLA/CNF/C30B 1% - 1% (PLA + cellulose nanofiber + nanoclay) were elaborated by solvent casting and characterized by different techniques. The CNF based composites showed better oxygen barrier properties and similar water barrier properties to C30B whereas the presence of both nanofillers showed a synergetic behaviour in terms of both water vapour and oxygen transmission rate.

Figure 1 WVTR and OTR of the nanocomposites

It was also found that all of the nanocomposites had higher degree of crystallinity than the neat PLA (Fig 2) due to the nucleating agent behaviour. Moreover it was found that the crystallinity achieved by the solvent casting procedure was different that the crystallinity achieved by isothermal crystallization, which might be consider as crystallinity achieved by industrially relevant techniques. The PLA and PLA/C30B 1% showed smaller spherulites size and a more homogeneous crystallinity than the PLA/CNF 1% and PLA/CNF/C30B 1% 1% which showed bigger spherulite size but less homogenous spherulite distribution, probably due to the different drying temperature (Fig 3).

In order to see the real effect of the nanofiller within the matrix for crystallinity achieved by industrially relevant techniques, the water barrier properties were measured after solvent, in amorphous state and after full crystallinity achieved by isothermal crystallization. To achieve almost amorphous composites the films were hot-pressed at 170 °C for 5 minutes with 5 minutes of preheat and fast cooled at room temperature. Two problems were found using this protocol. The first one was that after this process some imperfections appeared on the films and the second one was that the cooling was not fast enough to completely prevent the crystal formation due to cold crystallization process, as can be seen on Fig 2, but at least was enough to have films with very reasonable differences on the crystallinity. Finally those composites were heated for 2 hours at 120 °C in order to have completely crystallized nanocomposites. The temperature of 120 °C was chosen since at this temperature the nanocomposites showed faster crystallization behaviour making this temperature the more interesting for the industry.

The samples were labelled “PLA, PLA/C30B, PLA/CNF, PLA/CNF/C30B” + a suffix “SC” (Solvent casting), FC (Fully Crystallized) or “ANN” (Annealed).

Figure 2 Degree of the crystallinity of the nanocomposites after annealing, solvent casting and isothermal crystallization procedures.

Figure 3 of the nanocomposites after solvent casting (top), annealing (centre) and isothermal crystallization procedures (bottom).

The use of the QSM (Quartz Spring Microbalance) is an absorption based method and it has several advantages if compared with the methods based on used in previous publication as the “cup” method for the WVTR and a commercially available oxygen permeability tester, in which a molecule has to pass though the film.

- 1) The QSM does not provide data of the permeability but of the diffusivity and the sorption of the test vapour into material. If the material follows a simple model the permeability can be obtained from this data and the effect of both parameters can be studied thus having a better understanding of the material.
- 2) The QSM requires form a very small sample. Although after hot pressing the films were showing defects as long as this balance required from 2 cm² of samples was possible to find regions with no defects.
- 3) The QSM is more resistant to small defects in the films. In the classical analysis even a very tiny hole on the film will give completely different results since the oxygen could permeate from those

tiny holes. But in the case of the QSM tiny holes won't affect very seriously the measure since is based on absorption.

The QSM provides values of water sorption and water diffusivity, and the WVTR can be estimated using models. In this case the chosen model is the sorption-diffusion model, and according to this model the permeability can be calculated by means of Eq 3:

$$P=D*S \tag{3}$$

Where P is the permeability, D is the diffusivity and S is the solubility. In order to validate this model, the WVTR of the nanocomposites after solvent casting were measured using this method and the results were compared with the results obtained by the cup method (Fig 4).

Figure 4 Values of WVTR obtained by the QSM and "Cup" method

As can be seen there are slight difference on the overall WVTR if compared the cup method and the QSM, but the relative values are actually very accurate. Those small differences on the overall value can be explained by the fact that when using the cup method the desiccating agent (silica gel) actually does not absorb all of the water that cross the films thus giving slightly smaller values that it should. Finally the films made by solvent casting might have bubbles and they might not have a constant thickness, and this might lead to small errors.

Figure 5 Diffusivity of the nanocomposites after annealing, solvent casting and isothermal crystallization procedures.

From the Fig 5 it can be observed how all of the nanocomposites, in all of the cases show smaller diffusivity than the neat PLA meaning that the addition of the nanofillers has influence on the mass transport through the polymeric film. If compared PLA/CNF and PLA/C30B with same crystallinity conditions (amorphous and fully crystallized) can be realized that although the addition of clay decreases more the diffusivity than the CNF, the addition of CNF is not negligible proving that the CNF

has influence on the barrier properties on the nanocomposites. Moreover the hybrid nanocomposite PLA/CNF/C30B showed a huge decrease meaning that the decrease of the C30B and CNF are accumulative.

There is a dramatic decrease on the diffusivity from annealed samples to fully crystallized samples. This is due to the fact that the spherulites are essentially non permeable domains so they increase the tortuous path of the molecules. As can be noted for the composites after solvent casting, the Neat PLA-SC and the PLA/C30B-SC (solvent casting) nanocomposites shows similar diffusivity to Neat PLA-AM and PLA/C30B-AM (quenched nanocomposites), this might be explained for the fact the solvent casting procedure used to elaborate this nanocomposites was at low temperature and this lead to small spherulite size, and from this data can be deduced that the small spherulite size does not increase the tortuous path of the molecules substantially.

On the other hand the PLA/CNF-SC and PLA/CNF/C30B-SC nanocomposites were elaborated by solvent casting procedure too, but the drying was at higher temperature so the spherulite size was bigger. The results on diffusivity of those nanocomposites and the fully crystallized nanocomposites (big spherulites too) shows that the big spherulites could increase the tortuous path of the molecules within the matrix. Finally no clear relationship was found between diffusivity and relative humidity this means that the value of the diffusivity of the nanocomposites should remain constant at least in the range of 0-65% RH.

Figure 6 Water absorption of the nanocomposites after annealing, solvent casting and isothermal crystallization procedures

The calculation of the water sorption (Fig 6) was done through a sorption isotherm. From the experiments, the water sorption at 2-3 different relative humidity was calculated. Those results were plotted and the slope was considered as the sorption isotherm (the R² was ranging 0.9887 to 0.999) and from the slope the theoretical value of water sorption at 50% RH was interpolated. The experiments were done in the range of relative humidity of 0%-65/70% this range was chosen since above this relative humidity limit the isotherm was losing its linear behaviour.

When investigating the water sorption of the nanocomposites it was found that in all of the cases the water sorption was increasing from the amorphous sample to the fully crystallized one which is in agreement with some works which claims that the water uptake increases with the crystallinity. It was also found that addition of nanofillers was also enlarging the water sorption of the nanocomposites (although PLA-FC and PLA/C30B-FC showed the same water sorption, but this might be explained for the lower crystallinity of the PLA/C30B-FC). Finally the addition of CNF seems to increase more the water sorption than the C30B, probably due to the fact that the CNF is a more hydrophilic material than the C30B. But when comparing the nanocomposites after solvent casting it can be found very different behaviours, in one hand the PLA-SC and PLA/C30B-SC showed smaller water sorption than the PLA-AM and PLA/C30B-AM but in the other hand the PLA/CNF-FC and the PLA/CNF/C30B-FC showed much higher sorption than the quasi-amorphous samples and they were close to the fully

crystallized samples. Again, the difference might be attributed to a different spherulite size. While the PLA/CNF-FC and PLA/CNF/ C30B-FC shows big spherulites size like all of the FC (Fully Crystallized) samples the PLA-SC and the PLA/C30B-SC shows a very small spherulites size. Actually this might explain why in some articles is claimed that the PLA increases the water sorption with the crystallinity and in other is the opposite.

Figure 7 WVTR of the nanocomposites after annealing, solvent casting and isothermal crystallization procedures.

Finally if comparing the data from the WVTR (Fig 7) can be observed that there is a huge decrease on the WVTR when going from the amorphous composites to fully crystallized ones. This means that the decrease on the diffusivity due to high crystallinity is more important than the increase on water sorption, meaning that this is a diffusivity driven process. When comparing the WVTR PLA/C30B and PLA/CNF can be seen that either in amorphous state either in fully crystallized state the C30B based nanocomposites shows smaller WVTR than the CNF based nanocomposites meaning that the clay is better nanofiller than CNF in terms barrier properties, but it seems that the CNF has effect on the WVTR even at a low load as 1%. Finally the nanocomposite of PLA/CNF/C30B 1% 1% always showed a big improvement on terms of WVTR showing that the combination of clay and nanocellulose is a powerful method to enhance the barrier properties of the nanocomposites.

4 CONCLUSIONS

It was found that although the degree of crystallinity plays an important role in the barrier properties, the spherulites size plays also a role in terms of barrier properties. It seems that small spherulites size reducer the water sorption and does not affect as much the diffusivity as the big spherulites size which increases the water sorption. Regarding to nanocomposites it seems that the C30B is more promising than the CNF to improve the barrier properties although the effect of the CNF is not negligible; moreover the combination of both nanofillers seems to improve the barrier properties.

6 REFERENCES

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